

677 Swedish

MR - own knowledge, Andersson 1994

1. Segmental Properties

1.1 Phonotactic Patterns

-not more than 3 syllable initial C's allowed

-syllable final consonant clusters are simplified (i.e. -ndsk >

-nsk, -skt > -st, -igt > -it

-g, k, sk -> [j], [ç], [ʃ] before front vowels (only in stressed syllables)

-orthographic clusters containing <g> in final and generally also in medial position simplified rg -> rj, lg -> lj, ng -> ŋ, gn -> ŋn

-final -g weakened or loosed outside clusters as well,

-ig -> -i (sometimes even after other V's, i.e. 'jag 'I' [jɑ:], 'mig

[mej]

-initial clusters tj, kj -> [ç], gj,hj,lj -> [j], stj, skj, sj -> [ʃ]

1.2 Phonological Processes

-vowel harmony (Umlaut) is not productive

- retroflex consonants:

clusters of /r/ + dental C (t, d, s, n, l) are simplified to one retroflex C

as a result of this – and according to the rule that all (stressed) syllables are either V: or VCC a vowel before retroflex C gets lengthened, i.e. fjord [fju:d]

some exceptions to this rule, especially with /r+/s/, e.g. fors [fɔ̃s:]

"retroflexion rule" applies to all positions even over morpheme and word boundaries

retroflexion spreads over all following /t, d, s, n, l/ in a cluster, e.g. barn-s-lig [ba:ŋs̺li] 'childish'

1.3 Default Syllable Template

possible syllables:

CV:
CCV:
CCCV:
V:
V:C
VC: (or VCC)
VCCC (or VC:C)

Template: (C1C2C3)VC:(C) or (C1C2C3)V:(C)

C: =geminate or two different C's

no geminate syllabical initial

C3 must be sonorant

all (primary and secondary) stressed syllables are long (either V: or VCC), with the exception of some clusters containing a morphem boundary, e.g. *råd-s* council-GEN ['ro:ds]

2. Prosodic Properties

2.1 Stress

-primary stress in general on the first syllable (in native words),
secondary stress on the second syllable

-stress is attracted to V

-some derivational endings are stressed and remove the stress from the stem (or leaving behind tertiary stress)

-some derivations have secondary stress on the *sx* (similar to compounds)

2.2 Tone

-system of pitch accent = accent1 ("acute") on (original) monosyllabics, accent2 ("gravis") on (original) di-(or more)syllabic words (exceptions are loan words with stress on another than the first syllable)

^X*komma* 'to come' (inf.) [^X is accent2, 'is accent1; MR]

'kommer 'come' (prs.) (<Old Norse komr, kumr)

-compounds of two monosyllabics have accent2, i.e. '*bil* 'car',

'*tak* 'roof', ^X*biltak* 'roof of a car'

-morpho-syntactic function?

jf. a few minimal pairs such as

^X*tomte-n*

goblin-DEF

'the goblin' (Wicht, Kobold)

^X*tomt-en*

plot-DEF

'the plot (of land)'

3. Morpho-Syntax

3.1 Fusion

???

3.2 Non-Adjacent Allomorphy

stem allomorphy in verb inflection - as in other Germanic lgs
stem allomorphy in noun inflection, e.g. (Umlaut) *bok* 'book' vs.

böck-er book-PL; (Umlaut and accent shift) ^X*fader* 'father' vs.

fäder PL; (Umlaut and Quantity shift) *gås* [go:s] 'goose' vs.

gäss [jæs:] PL

suppletion in verb inflection - as in other Germanic lgs

3.3 Infixation, Circumfixation, Simulfixation

n.a.

3.4 Reduplication

n.a.

3.5 Clitics and Particles

???

4. Other Questions

4.1 Unstressed Vowels

unstressed V are short

no minimal pairs between long and short vowels because of the above mentioned rule (either V: or VCC)
unstressed /e/ reduced to schwa

4.2 Word-Word Combinations

-compounds of two accent1-words (monosyllabics) have accent2 (see above)

-linking vowel or linking -s- sometimes in compounds

-linking -s- always if first part of compound is complex itself, i.e. *hus-dörr* 'front door' (lit. 'house door'), *hus-dörr-s-nyckel* 'key of the front door'

-however, no -s- if first element of compound ends in /s, ʃ/ or in a cluster containing one of the two phonemes

-no -s- either if first element ends in vowel or unstressed vowel+/r, l, n/

no incorporation

complex predicates???

lots of particle-verb-combinations (?incorporations)

4.3 Bipartite Stems

n.a.

4.4 Periphrastic Morphology

periphrastic forms:

perfect, plusquamperfect, future, past future, future perfect, past future perfect

there is also a periphrastic passive (beside an inflexional one)

the template is AUX+inflected form

4.5 Pre- and Postpositions

prepositions, some prepositions can be used as postpositions, there are even some circumpositions

adpositions are free

MR:Add 2005-Febr-23

[',] =acut (main and secondary)

[^X] =grav accent/pitch accent

(WTID66) MorphDomain of

-Superheavy VCCC

stem: *svensk* [svɛnsk] 'swedish (common gender)'

stem+sx: *svenskt* [svɛnst] svensk-t 'swedish (neuter)'; *byggds* [bygds] bygg-d-s build-PRET-PASSIVE (note: as in the last two examples some stem+sx forms should actually result in VCCC.C, but syllable final consonant clusters are normally simplified - e.g. nskt > nst - or shortened - i.e. yggds > ygds)

-Superheavy V:CCC

stem+sx: *lägst* [lɛ:gst] läg-st low-SUPERLATIVE 'lowest'

Stem+Sx+sx *åkts* [o:kts] åk-t-s drive-PRET-PASSIVE

-Superheavy V:CC

(only) stem+Sx *stads.hus* [^Xsta:ds,hʉ:s] stad-s-hus town-GEN-house 'town hall'

(WTID65) MorphDomain of

-Min CV:

stem: *ta* [tɑ:] 'to take'

(WTID139) MorphDomain of

Exactly 1 Main Stress

px±stem±sx

??px±stem±particle

s.k. particle verbs have their stress on the particle:

(*jag*) **ser till** (*att du får...*) '(I) **make shure** (that you get...) [**se'tɪl:]**

compare:

(*jag*) **ser till** (*första delen*) '(I) **look to** (the first part)' [**se:,tɪl]**

(WTID64) MorphDomain of

Assim Retroflex(t)ion [MR:typo]

px±stem±sx: *barn-s-lig* child-GEN-DERIV ['bɑ:ŋʂ[ɪ] 'childish'

(compound) stem+stem±sx: *fjärrstyrd* fjärr-styr-d far-steer-PRET [^Xfjæ:.,ʂty:d] 'operated by remote controll'

(two words) stem+stem: *jag tror dativ är rätt* 'I believe dative is right' ['tro:.'dɑ:tɪf]

